

Hydrogen Bonding and the Stereochemistry of Hydrazones and Hydrazides derived from 1,3-Dicarbonyl Compounds involving Imino Nitrogen

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β -Diketones form hydrazones with N',N' -diacylhydrazines and exhibit a six-membered hydrogen bonded cyclic ketiminyll system involving the imino nitrogen. ^1H nmr spectra of the hydrazones obtained from N -amino- α, β - (9,10-dihydroanthracene-9,10-*endo*-diyl)succinimide and acetylacetone demonstrated restricted rotation about N—N bond and a planer hydrogen bonded cyclic system orthogonal to the succinimidyl plane. β -Ketoester behaved differently and reacted in enolic form to give intramolecularly hydrogen bonded hydrazide whose stereochemistry has been established with the help of an asymmetric cage moiety. Both hydrazones and hydrazides adopt Z -configuration about its olefinic part and the methyl of the ketimino or enamine takes a *syn*-orientation.

1,3-Dicarbonyl compounds are known to exist in tautomeric keto-enol forms in which enol form is stabilised by strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding¹. It was considered of interest to investigate the role of hydrogen bonding in controlling the stereochemistry and stability of hydrazones derived from 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds. In general, β -diketones and β -ketoesters give pyrazoles and pyrazolones, respectively, when reacted with hydrazine or monosubstituted hydrazines in presence of acids². In the absence of an active imino hydrogen different behaviour of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds has been observed. A number of compounds have been prepared by the reaction of three β -diketones and one β -ketoester with N -aminoimides derived from the Diels-Alder adducts of anthracene-maleic anhydride (1a—c and 4), 1,3-cyclopentadiene-M.A. (2 and 5) and 1,3,5-cycloheptatriene-M.A. (3 and 6). Stereochemistry of the compounds has been investigated with the help of an asymmetric cage moiety through ^1H nmr spectroscopy.

1a, 2, 3 ; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$
1b ; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{Ph}$
1c ; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{Ph}$

For (1a-c), (2) and (3) : For (4, 5) and (6) :

Results and Discussion

^1H nmr spectrum of compound 1a shows the methyl resonance as a sharp singlet at δ 0.75 (3H), which suggests a preferred 6-membered cyclic system containing the imino moiety orthogonal to the succinimidyl plane and in *syn*-orientation. Restricted rotation about N—N bond and preferred sp^2 -exocyclic nitrogen has earlier been demonstrated in a similar system³. Equivalence of α - and β -protons (δ 3.4, 2H, bs) suggests the symmetry about succinimidyl plane. The presence of enolic proton at δ 16.2 and an olefinic proton at δ 5.1(s) clearly shows that β -diketone has reacted with carbonyl site of enolic form and a flat, six-membered hydrogen bonded structure is evident from the spectral pattern. In this preferred conformation nitrogen lone-pair is *anti* to the cage due to strong repulsion between lone-pair of nitrogen and phenyl ring of the cage⁴. The two methyls are in the same plane and the overall system is in Z -configuration about olefinic moiety. Ir spectrum of compound 1a (ν_{max} 3 150 cm^{-1} for OH stretching) is in agreement with the intramolecular hydrogen bonding. ^1H nmr spectrum of 1b indicated that acetyl carbonyl is more reactive site for condensation (since only one product was obtained even after repeating the reaction a number of times) and suggested a similar intramolecularly hydrogen bonded six-membered cyclic system, orthogonal to the succinimidyl plane having the methyl group *syn*-orientation. Similar were the cases with compounds 1c, 2 and 3. In both the compounds 1b and 1c, the olefinic proton appears along with the cage aromatic protons due to being present in a highly conjugated system. In compounds 2 and 3 one of the methyls attached to the imino group experiences the anisotropic interaction of the olefinic bond of the cage and appears at a shielded position (δ 1.72). Equivalence of 2,3-protons in 2 and 6,7-protons in 3 supports the symmetry of the molecules.

A similar analysis of their ^1H nmr spectra reveals that a cyclic structure as observed in 1a, is also present in compounds 4–6 due to strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between enamino proton and ester carbonyl group, as substantiated by the presence of NH resonance at low field (δ 9.92). In compounds 4–6 it is intramolecular hydrogen bonding which controls the overall stereochemistry and stability of the molecule and gives rise to the proposed geometry possessing Z-configuration about olefinic system. Due to hydrogen bonding inversion of nitrogen lone-pair in sp^2 -hybridised state is not possible and the resulting hydrazones do not exhibit E-Z isomerisation.

Experimental

Nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a JEOL FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer at 25° using tetramethyl silane as an internal standard and ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyser. All the compounds gave satisfactory analytical results for C and H.

Preparation of compounds: The Diels-Alder adducts of maleic anhydride and each of anthracene⁵, 1,3-cyclopentadiene⁶ and 1,3,5-cycloheptatriene⁷ were prepared as per literature. The N-aminosuccinimides of the adducts were also prepared according to the reported method⁸. Compounds 1–6 were prepared by refluxing the aforesaid N-aminosuccinimides separately with equimolar amounts of the β -dicarbonyl compound in presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in ethanol for 15–20 h. The β -dicarbonyl compounds used were acetyl acetone for 1a, 2 and 3, benzoyl acetone for 1b, dibenzoyl methane for 1c and ethyl acetoacetate for 4–6. M.ps., ir and ^1H nmr spectral data of the compounds are as follows: 1a, m.p. 186–88°, ν_{max} 3 150, 1 780, 1 720, 1 630 cm^{-1} , δ 0.75 and 2.1 (3H, s each, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 3.4 (2H, bs, α - and β -H), 5.0 (2H, bs, 9- and 10-H), 5.1 (1H, s, olefinic), 7.3–7.8 (8H, m, aromatic), 16.2 (1H, s, enolic); 1b, m.p. 214–16°, ν_{max} 3 170, 1 780, 1 720, 1 620 cm^{-1} , δ 1.18 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.4 (2H, bs, α - and β -H), 5.05 (2H, bs, 9- and 10-H), 7.25–8.10 (14H, m, aromatic and olefinic), 16.8 (1H, s, enolic); 1c, m.p. 220–23°, ν_{max} 3 160, 1 780, 1 710, 1 630 cm^{-1} , δ 3.38 (2H, bs, α - and β -H), 5.0 (2H, bs, 9- and 10-H), 7.1–8.4 (19H, m, aromatic and olefinic), 17.1 (1H, s, enolic); 2, m.p. 192–94°, λ_{max} 3 220,

1 780, 1 720, 1 660 cm^{-1} , δ 1.72 and 2.15 (3H, s each, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 1.5–1.82 (2H, ABq, J 10 Hz, 7- CH_2), 3.42 (2H, bs, 2- and 3-H), 3.5 (2H, bs, 1- and 4-H), 5.28 (1H, s, olefinic), 6.35 (2H, t, J 1.5 Hz, 5- and 6-H), 16.0 (1H, s, enolic); 3, m.p. 145–46°, ν_{max} 3 110, 1 785, 1 720, 1 650 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.32 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 1.15 (2H, m, 2- and 4-H), 1.72 and 2.1 (3H, s each, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 3.12 (2H, bs, 6- and 7-H), 3.6 (2H, bs, 1- and 5-H), 5.37 (1H, s, olefinic), 6.0 (2H, t, J 1.5 Hz, 8- and 9-H), 16.4 (1H, s, enolic); 4, m.p. 176–78°, ν_{max} 3 220, 1 790, 1 715, 1 660 cm^{-1} , δ 0.68 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.27 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 3.4 (2H, bs, α - and β -H), 4.26 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 4.78 (1H, s, olefinic), 5.1 (2H, bs, 9- and 10-H), 7.3–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 9.92 (1H, s, NH); 5, m.p. 170–71°, ν_{max} 3 110, 1 780, 1 720, 1 650 cm^{-1} , δ 1.28 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.72 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.5–1.8 (2H, ABq, J 10 Hz, 7- CH_2), 3.4 (2H, bs, 1- and 4-H), 3.5 (2H, bs, 2- and 3-H), 4.2 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 4.85 (1H, s, olefinic), 6.28 (2H, t, J 1.5 Hz, 5- and 6-H), 9.82 (1H, s, NH); 6, m.p. 155–58°, ν_{max} 3 150, 1 785, 1 730, 1 650 cm^{-1} , δ 0.28 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 1.15 (2H, m, 2- and 4-H), 1.25 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 1.72 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.16 (2H, bs, 6- and 7-H), 3.6 (2H, bs, 1- and 5-H), 4.25 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 4.81 (1H, s, olefinic), 6.0 (2H, t, J 1.5 Hz, 8- and 9-H), 9.85 (1H, s, NH).

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